

PVC-BASED POLYMER NANOCOMPOSITES: PROCESSING, FRACTURE AND CYCLIC FATIGUE

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SUMMARY

Nanoparticulate calcium carbonate was mechanically combined with PVC in varying volume fractions. The bonding strength between the particulate phase and the matrix was also varied. It was found that increasing the particulate content improves the toughness of the composite but this effect is reduced when interfacial bonding between the particles and matrix is improved; strength and stiffness show inverse behaviour. Modelling reveals that toughening is associated with hysteretic energy absorption processes associated with cavitation. Interestingly, the addition of nanoparticulate phase has no noticeable effect upon cyclic fatigue crack growth.

Keywords: polyvinylchloride, calcium carbonate, nanocomposites, fracture, fatigue

ABSTRACT

Polyvinyl chloride (PVC) is a commodity polymer which is used for a wide range of applications in which structural performance is of primary importance. One application is for the transport of reticulating water in which many thousands of kilometres of PVC pipes are used. Strength, stiffness and toughness are the critical mechanical properties for this application. The introduction of nanometer-sized particles to form polymer nanocomposites has been demonstrated to lead to an increase in these mechanical properties in a range of systems [1]. However, these improvements are only realised with proper dispersion of the particles within the polymer. Achievement of this dispersion has proven to be a challenging problem in many systems.

Processing

PVC-based polymer nanocomposites were formed by added calcium carbonate, a common PVC filler (average particle size was 60 nm), in nanoparticulate form to PVC K57 resins with Ca-Zn based thermal stabilizers and lubricants. 3, 6, 9, 12 and 20 parts per hundred of resin (phr) by weight of nanoparticle CaCO₃ in a dry blend. A further series was processed by adding 0.6 phr titanate coupling agent to improve particle/matrix adhesion. A monolithic sample containing no nanoparticles was also manufactured along with a reference m-PVC, which contained 6 phr of CPE rubbery particles. Dry powder blends were processed on a two roll-mill operating then granulated into flakes using a bench-top mechanical granulator. The flakes were then molded into rectangular sheets by compression molding.

Characterisation Methods and Results

Transmission electron micrographs of the samples revealed the microstructure of the samples. It was found that good particle dispersion occurred at low concentrations

(<9 phr) and improved with the addition of the titanate compound with concentrations up to 20 phr showing good dispersion.

Elastic modulus increased with nanoparticulate content and followed a Kerner prediction. Strength was found to decrease with increasing nanoparticulate content and be slightly higher in samples that contained titanate. Impact energy and toughness were found, however, to increase with nanoparticulate content, with the samples containing titanate showing slightly lower values. In all cases, stiffness and strength were higher than m-PVC and toughness was lower, with the exception of the 20 phr samples. Scanning electron micrographs of the fracture surfaces revealed extensive cavitation around the nanoparticulate particles which was not present when titanates were added to the mixture during processing. Cyclic fatigue crack growth measurements revealed that fatigue behaviour was unaffected by the addition of or fraction of nanoparticulate phase. Furthermore, the addition of titanates had no influence on fatigue behaviour. Slight improvements were observed compared with m-PVC.

Figure 1 Impact fracture surfaces of 6 phr PVC/CaCO₃ polymer nanocomposites with (right) and without (left) titanate coupling agent

Figure 2 Cyclic fatigue crack growth rates as function of stress intensity factor amplitude

Discussion and Conclusions

The addition of nanoparticulate filler appears to enhance cavitation associated with plastic deformation. This leads to an increase in toughness, especially when there is weak bonding between the nanoparticles and the filler. An improvement in adhesion resulting from the addition of the titanates, improves particulate dispersion but leads to a deterioration in toughness as cavitation is reduced. Modelling reveals that this is associated with the hysteretic energy absorption processes associated with cavitation. The reduced bonding between the particles and matrix, however, leads to a reduction in strength which may also be attributed to increased agglomeration in these samples. It appears that the nanoparticulate phase has no extraordinary effect upon stiffness beyond that expected from rule of mixtures influences.

References

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